

Table 1: Summary of the thematic analysis

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
1. Emergency preparedness			
Disaster Risk Anticipation and Foresight	Strengthening monitoring, surveillance, and early warning systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conducting risks and vulnerability assessment • Promoting research and development and investing in essential public health functions including those needed for all-hazards emergency risk management • Enhancing surveillance strategies (early case detection, investigation, isolation, and referrals; alert and rumor management, contact tracing, and community-based surveillance) • Decentralizing contact tracing and supporting regional and district teams • Training of Rapid Response Teams for effective operational response • Leveraging technology to facilitate contact tracing efforts and real-time electronic data analysis and transmission • Enhancing data stewardship and data governance systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Williams, Fahy, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Haldane <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Arabi <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Kuguyo <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Abubakar <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Gebremeskel, <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Aisyah <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Chang <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Fawole <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Wang <i>et al.</i>, 2021a • Moonasar <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Sundararaman <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Binagwaho <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Mghamba <i>et al.</i>, 2023
Emergency protocols	Procedures and guidelines to follow in the event of pandemics or emergencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and implementation of emergency protocols including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Emergency Preparedness and Response Plans (EPRPs), checklists and protocols – Clinical tools and guidelines for infectious disease case management – Guidelines for personal hygiene, surveillance, contact tracing, quarantine, diagnosis, and laboratory tests – Disaster response/management toolkit for scalability and surge capacities – Public health emergency contingency plans for Ports of entry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Hunte <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Zikargae, 2020 • Mghamba <i>et al.</i>, 2023

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
Preparedness of critical sectors	National critical infrastructure in anticipation of epidemics and pandemics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening logistics and supply chain management • Expanding national ICU capacity. • Creating strategic reserves of essential equipment and health products • Developing the capacity to produce medical countermeasures for epidemic-prone diseases. • Prioritizing domestic production capacity for medical equipment, pharmaceuticals, vaccines, and drug discovery. • Investing in integrated health infrastructures • Establishing public policies and regulatory frameworks for healthcare digitization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Arabi <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • William <i>et al.</i>, 2022c • Balde <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Gouya <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Ven Ginneken <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Gebremeskel, <i>et al.</i>, 2021
2: Management of crisis			
Crisis Communication	Communication and engagement with the public and communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Timely, transparent, and accurate government communication • Establishment of dedicated hotlines and communication channels • Development of communication materials and apps • Social mobilization and sensitization campaigns through partnerships with CSOs • Monitoring and addressing misinformation • Stakeholder participation and engagement, involving community influencers • Forming partnerships with social media companies and mobile network providers to disseminate key health messages. • Addressing stigma and resistance through intensive social awareness campaigns • Tailoring messages and campaigns to specific populations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Babe <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Ha <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Mghamba <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Thomas <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Abubakar <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Al Siyabi <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Alami <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Alava & Guevara, 2021 • Bloomstone <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Chhim <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Corbin <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Thu <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Zikargae, 2020 • Moonasar <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Akande <i>et al.</i>, 2023
Governance arrangements	Country-level response coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-level political leadership and sustained commitment • Establishment of the National Steering Committee (NSC) for COVID-19 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Thomas <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Sagan <i>et al.</i>, 2022

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activation of NPHEOC • Clear chain of command, accountability, and strategic direction • Regular media briefings and communication through television, radio, websites, and social media • Data-driven decision-making and evidence-informed guidelines and efficient information management • Strengthening coordination platforms and involving relevant sectors (a whole-of-government approach) • Development of COVID-19 Preparedness and Response Plans aligned with the National Response Framework • Effective governance frameworks emphasizing transparency and accountability • Coordinating response beyond national borders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forsgren <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Fleming <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Gouya <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Ha <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Haldane <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Hunte <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Mghamba <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Alami <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Assefa, Woldeyohannes, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Bigoni <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Burke <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Kluge <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Coccia, 2022; • Desson, Lambertz, <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Desson, Weller, <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Djalante <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Tille <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Thu <i>et al.</i>, 2022
Whole-of-Society Response	Institutionalising mechanism for multi-sectoral and multidisciplinary response	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fostering multi-sectoral and multi-disciplinary response <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Collaborating with the private sector, academia, civil societies, etc – Partnership with international agencies and organisations – Inclusive engagement of communities through partnership with local leaders and influencers – Transparent communication, collaboration within the health system, and partnerships with external groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Aisyah <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Bloomstone <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Babe <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Haldane <i>et al.</i>, 2021
3. Response and recovery			
Lockdown and restrictions	Implementation of containment, isolation, and mitigation measures to reduce the spread of infection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Declaration of a state of emergency and implementation of stringent lockdown measures • Intensive testing and case confirmation • Contact tracing and isolation of infected persons • Enforcement of non-pharmaceutical measures (social distancing, confinement, personal hygiene, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Khanna <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Kavanagh, <i>et al.</i> 2021 • Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Amin Tabish, 2020 • Kuguyo <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Emahi <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Beesley <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Binagwaho <i>et al.</i>, 2020

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
		<p>handwashing, hand sanitizing, and use of masks in public places).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental disinfection • Ban on public and mass social gatherings • Travel bans (air, road, and sea transportation) • Closure of businesses, industries, and schools • Workplace monitoring and screening for COVID-19 symptoms • Provision of mandatory WASH materials at entrances of work and commercial places 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chang <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Desson, Weller, <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Džakula <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Tille <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Webb, Winkelmann, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Moonasar <i>et al.</i>, 2021
	Ports of Entry (PoEs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closure of national borders • Ensuring compliance with WHO IHR at the PoEs • Strengthening screening and surveillance at PoEs • Case detection, mandatory quarantine, and surveillance reporting for international arrivals • Availability of information, education, and communication materials at PoEs, including thermal scanners and infrared thermometers • PCR tests and rapid antigen tests conducted for inbound and outbound travellers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Kuguyo <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Alava & Guevara, 2021 • Binagwaho <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Tabish, 2020 • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Wang <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Wang, <i>et al.</i>, 2020

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
Economic and Financial Support	Financing mechanisms to provide stability of health system and relief for businesses and households	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring the uninterrupted flow of funds to support outbreak preparedness and response • Implementation of tax-based measures including tax relief, deferred tax reporting, and income tax payment for individuals and small enterprises • Reduction in interest rates for citizens and businesses and soft loans to local manufacturing companies • Drawing on financial reserves, budget reallocations, and borrowing • Funding support from development partners • Creation of a special fund for COVID-19 response • Increasing budgetary allocations to the health sector • Adapting payment systems to the new environment • Minimizing opportunities for corruption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bhatia & Abraham, 2022 • Thomas <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Alami <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Sagan <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Elbeshbishi <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Fagher & Abiari, 2020 • Haldane <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Desson, Lambertz, <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Desson, Weller, <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Adebis <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Djalante <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • United Nations, 2021
Social policies	Social protection measures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social assistance: cash and other in-kind transfer • Social insurance: health protection, social security, unemployment insurance • Labour market subsidies (special allowances or grants, wage subsidies, leave benefits) • Access to basic services (housing, water, sanitation electricity, education, etc) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hunte <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Baptista <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Iyer <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • United Nations, 2021 • Béland <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Aidukaite_ <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Webb, Winkelmann, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Banda Chitsamatanga & Malinga, 2021

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
Health Measures	Human Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mobilizing and recruiting additional health workers and volunteers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Increasing recruitment quotas. – Utilising final-year medical and nursing students for support. – Bringing back retired health professionals. – Seeking assistance from other countries or organizations. • Scaling-up capacity among the existing health workforce <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Extending working hours and changing contracts. – Temporarily cancelling leave and modifying registration requirements. • Protecting health workers from physical, mental, and financial pressures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Implementing hygiene measures in healthcare facilities. – Regular testing to identify and control infections. – Providing financial and social support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sagan <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Chua <i>et al.</i> 2020 • Kavanagh, <i>et al.</i> 2021 • Williams, Maier, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Williams, Scarpetti, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Ginneken <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Fleming <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Gouya <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Burau <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Haldane <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Huntet <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Winkelmann, Panteli <i>et al.</i>, 2022; • Winkelmann, Webb, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Alami <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Assefa, Gilks, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Buchan <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Džakula <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Tille <i>et al.</i>, 2022
	Maintaining essential health service delivery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skill-mix changes to shift primary care tasks to nurses • Leveraging primary health care for essential services • Introducing new care pathways to reach patients • Providing guidelines for service continuity during outbreaks, • Utilizing the private sector to augment capacity • Implementing teleconsultations and digital health tools to support service delivery 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assaye & Shimie, 2022 • Webb, Lenormand, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Thomas <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Gouya <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Mghamba <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Williams, Fahy, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Alami <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Assefa, Gilks, <i>et al.</i>, 2022
	Case management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deployment of experts, training, and SOPs • Increasing critical care capacity • Establishing centres for effective clinical management of COVID-19 cases • Home-based isolation and management of COVID-19 cases • Postponing elective treatments and surgeries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Olu <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Ha <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Huntet <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Winkelmann, Panteli <i>et al.</i>, 2022; Winkelmann, Webb, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Khanna <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Okeke <i>et al.</i>, 2020

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
	Facility-based infection prevention and control (IPC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing hospital networks, both within countries and across borders • Limiting healthcare facility visits • Conducting screening for COVID-19 symptoms • Strengthening IPC through capacity building, and environmental control. • Developing and implementing IPC response plans and guidelines • Improving access to WASH services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Olu <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Khanna <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Balde <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Abu & Elliott, 2022
	Operational support and logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Block-booking private hospital beds, equipment, and staff to increase capacity • Repurposing non-health facilities and establishing temporary facilities to accommodate mild cases • Repurposing surgical rooms, anaesthesia machines, and clinics for critical care • Refurbishing designated hospitals as COVID-19 isolation centres • Building purpose-built facilities with integrated functions for infectious disease management • Ensuring the appropriate distribution of resources (consumables, devices, and pharmaceuticals) • Leveraging technology for efficient resource management • Utilizing dedicated global platforms for procurement and logistic support to secure essential equipment, medicines, and supplies • Securing support, including donations from local and international organizations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Olu <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Williams, Fahy, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • ven Ginneken <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Haldane <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Mghamba <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Winkelmann, Panteli <i>et al.</i>, 2022; • Winkelmann, Webb, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Chua <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Hunte <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Alava & Guevara, 2021 • Bhaskar <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Džakula <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Wang <i>et al.</i>, 2020 • Wasswa <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Webb, Winkelmann <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Moonasar <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Khanna <i>et al.</i>, 2020
	Laboratory diagnosis and management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing and strengthening in-country laboratory networks • Implementing a robust system of large-scale testing for epidemic control • Leveraging existing laboratory infrastructure and diagnostics industry to expand testing capacity • Repurposing research facilities and resources to expand laboratory centres during the pandemic • Collaborating with the private sector to enhance testing capabilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talisuna <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Dzinamarira <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Lanyero <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Tabish, 2020 • Balde <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Okeke, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Aisyah <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Tessema <i>et al.</i>, 2021 • Tille <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Webb, Winkelmann, <i>et al.</i>, 2022

Sub-theme	Key areas of focus	Response Strategies	Sources
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decentralizing laboratory capacity through peripheral district laboratories • Shifting from manual RNA extraction to an automated system for quicker results using a pooling system • Leveraging technology to deploy rapid diagnostic tests 	
	Vaccine management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing and implementing vaccination plans and programmes • Prioritizing high-risk groups in the initial phase of vaccination efforts • Utilizing the existing primary healthcare supply chain to boost vaccination efforts • Leveraging existing immunization structure to expand vaccination • Fostering partnerships with various stakeholders to expand coverage and enhance vaccine equity • Domestic production of COVID-19 vaccines • Massive advocacy and risk communication to minimize vaccine hesitancy • Utilising digital health tools for the effective rollout of vaccination programmes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Olu <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Williams, Fahy, <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Gouya <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Alava & Guevara, 2021 • Amani <i>et al.</i>, 2023 • Bloomstone <i>et al.</i>, 2022 • Zhang <i>et al.</i>, 2022